

The Unjournal

Evaluation 2 of "The Returns To Science In The Presence Of Technological Risks" by Matt Clancy

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Summary assessment

Criterion	Percentile ranking	CI
Advancing our knowledge and practice	65	30-100
Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness	60	45-75
Logic and communication	50	30-70
Open, collaborative, replicable science	60	35-85
Real-world relevance	70	50-90
Relevance to global priorities	90	80-100
	Journal tier	
What journal ranking tier should this work be published in?	4.5	3-5
What journal ranking tier will this work be published in?	2	0-4

Paper summary

'The Returns To Science In The Presence Of Technological Risks' by Matt Clancy considers whether the benefits of science outweigh its risks by modelling the welfare effects of globally pausing science for one year. The benefits considered are increases in per capita income and a decreasing mortality rate. The risks are advances in biotechnology which might enable malicious actors to create dangerous pathogens. These risks are modelled as an increased rate of mortality due to more frequent, more severe pandemics and as a risk of extinction due to a pandemic killing the entire human population. In a model without extinction risk, the benefits of science strongly outweigh the risks. It thus seems that the qualitative result when ignoring the possibility of science increasing extinction risk are not sensitive to parameter choices. When extinction risk is accounted for, the conclusions depend on how valuable one reckons the possible future of humanity (which would be lost due to extinction) to be.

In this evaluation I focus on the choice of model parameters. To introduce the parameters, I briefly summarise the report's model. Welfare effects are computed based on the following infinite period model:

$$V = \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} p^t n_t u(y_t)$$

Here, y_t is per capita income in year t , $u(y_t)$ is the utility experienced by an individual alive in a year in which per capita income is y_t and n_t is the population size in year t . p is a discount factor (see discussion below). y_t grows at rate G each year. If science is paused now, the income growth temporarily drops to g in T years before growing again at G afterwards. Population size n_t grows at constant rate s until in t_1 years, the "time of perils" commences and population growth is reduced to $s - d$, where d represents excess mortality due to the perils of biotechnology. When science is paused for one year, this time of perils commences one year later than it otherwise would have. Besides, the constancy of the population growth rate at s (or $s - d$ during the time of perils) is based on the assumption that the birth rate and the mortality move in lockstep. However, pausing science for one year temporarily slows the decline of the mortality rate attributable to scientific progress after T years without affecting the birth rate. The result is a permanent decline in the net population growth rate to \bar{s} . The returns to science in this baseline model are large and positive and remain large when science's effect on health are modeled more realistically in section 6. In section 8, a version of the model with extinction risk is considered, where there is an annual extinction risk of d_x applying during the time of perils. Section 9 considers an extension where science reduces both d and d_x .

General comments

While it is unsurprising that the version of the model without extinction risk stipulates large returns to science that are almost unaffected by the time of perils (see the results of the modified model in section 6), an important contribution of the report is to establish a threshold the value of the future of humanity must exceed to warrant pausing science when science contributes to extinction risk (section 8). An important result is also the the threshold the annual reduction in extinction risk due to science has to exceed in order for the net impact of science (after accounting for the fact that science also bring about the time of perils) to be positive. Overall, the methodology of the paper is transparent and well explained. The author appropriately balanced tractability with realistic modelling. The author considers a number of extensions to his baseline model that address particular considerations. However some considerations are left out of the model, e.g. animal welfare (the current value of humanity might be negative because of factory farming) and how utility depends on the total population size (in the current model, the flow value is proportional to the population size). There may be minor flaws in arguing for certain parameter choices (see my comments on parameter choices below).

Comments on parameter choices

The author carefully justifies his choice of parameters making reference to the academic literature as well as to forecasts of superforecasters and experts who participated in the Existential Risk Persuasion Tournament (XPT). For some parameters (in particular p) it might be worthwhile to conduct robustness checks with alternative

values, at least in the model which includes extinction risk. In the following, I summarise how the author chooses each parameter and offer some commentary.

Label	Value	Author's reasoning	Comment
G	1%	The author first reasons with reference to the economic literature that the past growth trend of 2% was in part due to temporary factors and only 1% was due to scientific progress. He thus chooses $G = 1\%$ but then states: 'An additional 1% likely will come from other factors, but since this growth is baked in, we can usually ignore it when comparing counterfactual policies'	If the author believes that growth will actually continue to be 2% then why not choose 2%? That would be cleaner. The argument that the additional 1% is 'baked in' would also apply to the first 1%.
g	0.75%	This number is obtained by based on the number of patents that directly or indirectly rely on science and how important science plausibly is for a patent's contribution to economic growth.	The argument put forward by the author would also apply to a permanent halt in science. If science was stopped permanently would we expect an only slightly lower long run growth rate than if science continues? I find $g = 0$ a plausible choice.

<p><i>d</i></p>	<p>0.0021% and 0.0385%</p>	<p>The author infers annual probabilities of pandemics in different bins of severity from superforecasters' and domain experts' subjective probabilities of such pandemics occurring over different time horizons and combines these probabilities with guesses of mortality rates for each bin. (E.g. he assumes that pandemics killing 1 – 10% of the population kill 2% on average.)</p>	<p>The author sets the mortality of pandemics killing 0 – 1% of the population to 0. However, a significant part of mortality risk from pandemics may stem precisely from such pandemics. (E.g. Covid killed less than 1% of the world population over a period of several years.) Instead of assuming levels of average mortality for each pandemic bin, one might consider assuming a particular distribution family for the annual distribution of mortality due to biological hazards, calibrate the distribution based on the percentiles implied by superforecasters' and domain experts' probabilities, respectively, and compute the resulting expected mortality.</p>
<p><i>p</i></p>	<p>0.98</p>	<p>This discount factor is not intended to discount the utility of future generations relative to today's utility. Instead it aims to account for the chance that general conditions change so fundamentally that our expectation of the impact of pausing science on flow utility becomes 0. This change in 'epistemic regime' is brought about by factors unrelated to whether science is paused or not. The author computes this probability as the sum of an annual</p>	

probability of transformative AI (1.6%), a major economic break (0.3%) and extinction risk from causes other than AI (0.08) yielding a discount rate of $\approx 2\%$.

I agree with the author's approach not to discount based on pure time preference. The author considers several alternative ways of deriving this discount rate. First, he turns to the probabilities participants of the XPT tournament gave to the event of observing 15% annual economic growth within certain time horizons as a proxy for the arrival of transformative AI as well as participants' probabilities of a major catastrophe. This yields discount rates in the range 0.05 – 0.7%. He then dismisses these discount rates arguing that 'the XPT only asked for forecasts through 2100 [...], and it may be inappropriate to extrapolate their forecasts forward by thousands of years.' However, the 2% discount rate he ends up adopting is mainly driven by the 1.6% annual probability of transformative AI arriving derived from the Open Philanthropy Worldview contest which assembled participants' credences of AGI arriving *before 2043*. Hence it is subject to the same criticism. Besides, to the extent that extinction risk is not constant (as the this criticism would suggest), choosing a rate close to the current one is the right thing to do since the future extinction rate

<p>probably makes a small difference to results. A lower discount rate p as implied by XPT participants' judgments would probably lower the threshold the value of the future of humanity has to exceed to make pausing science worthwhile when taking into account existential risk in section 8. It might be interesting to know these threshold values for lower values of p.</p>			
d_x	0.00016% and 0.02286%	Inferred from XPT participants' beliefs about probability of extinction through a pandemic.	This parameter might be considered a lower bound as it does not account for any contributions to other existential risks that science makes.
T	74	see paper	
s	0.6%	see paper	
\bar{s}	0.5967%	see paper	
t_1	17 – 18 years	see paper	

Parameter choices and comments